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A REVIEW ON EVALUATION METRICS FOR DATA CLASSIFICATION EVALUATIONS

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ABSTRACT

Evaluation metric plays a critical role in achieving the optimal classifier during the classification training. Thus, a selection of suitable evaluation metric is an important key for discriminating and obtaining the optimal classifier. This paper systematically reviewed the related evaluation metrics that are specifically designed as a discriminator for optimizing generative classifier. Generally, many generative classifiers employ accuracy as a measure to discriminate the optimal solution during the classification training. However, the accuracy has several weaknesses which are less distinctiveness, less discriminability, less informativeness and bias to majority class data. This paper also briefly discusses other metrics that are specifically designed for discriminating the optimal solution. The shortcomings of these alternative metrics are also discussed. Finally, this paper suggests five important aspects that must be taken into consideration in constructing a new discriminator metric.

KEYWORDS

Evaluation Metric, Accuracy, Optimized Classifier, Data Classification Evaluation

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Sentiment Analysis for Movies Reviews Dataset Using Deep Learning Models

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ABSTRACT

Due to the enormous amount of data and opinions being produced, shared and transferred everyday across the internet and other media, Sentiment analysis has become vital for developing opinion mining systems. This paper introduces a developed classification sentiment analysis using deep learning networks and introduces comparative results of different deep learning networks. Multilayer Perceptron (MLP) was developed as a baseline for other networks results. Long short-term memory (LSTM) recurrent neural network, Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) in addition to a hybrid model of LSTM and CNN were developed and applied on IMDB dataset consists of 50K movies reviews files. Dataset was divided to 50% positive reviews and 50% negative reviews. The data was initially pre-processed using Word2Vec and word embedding was applied accordingly. The results have shown that, the hybrid CNN_LSTM model have outperformed the MLP and singular CNN and LSTM networks. CNN_LSTM have reported the accuracy of 89.2% while CNN has given accuracy of 87.7%, while MLP and LSTM have reported accuracy of 86.74% and 86.64 respectively. Moreover, the results have elaborated that the proposed deep learning models have also outperformed SVM, Naïve Bayes and RNTN that were published in other works using English datasets.

KEYWORDS

Deep learning, LSTM, CNN, Sentiment Analysis, Movies Reviews, Binary Classification

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Categorization of Factors Affecting Classification Algorithms Selection

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ABSTRACT

A lot of classification algorithms are available in the area of data mining for solving the same kind of problem with a little guidance for recommending the most appropriate algorithm to use which gives best results for the dataset at hand. As a way of optimizing the chances of recommending the most appropriate classification algorithm for a dataset, this paper focuses on the different factors considered by data miners and researchers in different studies when selecting the classification algorithms that will yield desired knowledge for the dataset at hand. The paper divided the factors affecting classification algorithms recommendation into business and technical factors. The technical factors proposed are measurable and can be exploited by recommendation software tools.

KEYWORDS

Classification, Algorithm selection, Factors, Meta-learning, Landmarking

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Implementation of Risk Analyzer Model for Undertaking the Risk Analysis of Proposed Building Projects for a Selected Client

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ABSTRACT

The model of RISK ANALYZER was implemented as Knowledge-based System for the purpose of undertaking risk analysis for proposed construction projects in a selected domain. The Fuzzy Decision Variables (FDVs) that cause differences between initial and final contract sums of building projects were identified, the likelihood of the occurrence of the risks were determined and a Knowledge-Based System that would rank the risks was constructed using JAVA programming language and Graphic User Interface. The Knowledge-Based System is composed a Knowledge Base for storing data, an Inference Engine for controlling and directing the use of knowledge for problem-solution, and a User Interface that assists the user retrieve, use and alter data in the Knowledge Base. The developed Knowledge-Based System was compiled, implemented and validated with data of previously completed projects. The client could utilize the Knowledge-Based System to undertake proposed building projects

KEYWORDS

RISK ANALYZER, Risk analysis, Knowledge-Based Systems, JAVA, Graphic User Interface

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DATA MINING IN EDUCATION : A REVIEW ON THE KNOWLEDGE DISCOVERY PERSPECTIVE

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ABSTRACT

Knowledge Discovery in Databases is the process of finding knowledge in massive amount of data where data mining is the core of this process. Data mining can be used to mine understandable meaningful patterns from large databases and these patterns may then be converted into knowledge. Data mining is the process of extracting the information and patterns derived by the KDD process which helps in crucial decision-making. Data mining works with data warehouse and the whole process is divided into action plan to be performed on data: Selection, transformation, mining and results interpretation. In this paper, we have reviewed Knowledge Discovery perspective in Data Mining and consolidated different areas of data mining, its techniques and methods in it.

KEYWORDS

Decision, Knowledge, Mining, Selection, Transformation, Warehouse

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Increased Prediction Accuracy in The Game Of Cricket using Machine Learning

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ABSTRACT

Player selection is one the most important tasks for any sport and cricket is no exception. The performance of the players depends on various factors such as the opposition team, the venue, his current form etc. The team management, the coach and the captain select 11 players for each match from a squad of 15 to 20 players. They analyze different characteristics and the statistics of the players to select the best playing 11 for each match. Each batsman contributes by scoring maximum runs possible and each bowler contributes by taking maximum wickets and conceding minimum runs. This paper attempts to predict the performance of players as how many runs will each batsman score and how many wickets will each bowler take for both the teams. Both the problems are targeted as classification problems where number of runs and number of wickets are classified in different ranges. We used naïve bayes, random forest, multiclass SVM and decision tree classifiers to generate the prediction models for both the problems. Random Forest classifier was found to be the most accurate for both the problems.

KEYWORDS

Naïve Bayes, Random Forest, Multiclass SVM, Decision Trees, Cricket

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Incremental Learning: Areas and Methods – A Survey

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ABSTRACT

While the areas of applications in data mining are growing substantially, it has become extremely necessary for incremental learning methods to move a step ahead. The tremendous growth of unlabeled data has made incremental learning take up a big leap. Starting from BI applications to image classifications, from analysis to predictions, every domain needs to learn and update. Incremental learning allows to explore new areas at the same time performs knowledge amassing. In this paper we discuss the areas and methods of incremental learning currently taking place and highlight its potentials in aspect of decision making. The paper essentially gives an overview of the current research that will provide a background for the students and research scholars about the topic.

KEYWORDS

Incremental, learning, mining, supervised, unsupervised, decision-making

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A BUSINESS INTELLIGENCE PLATFORM IMPLEMENTED IN A BIG DATA SYSTEM EMBEDDING DATA MINING: A CASE OF STUDY

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ABSTRACT

In this work is discussed a case study of a business intelligence –BI- platform developed within the framework of an industry project by following research and development –R&D- guidelines of ‘Frascati’. The proposed results are a part of the output of different jointed projects enabling the BI of the industry ACI Global working mainly in roadside assistance services. The main project goal is to upgrade the information system, the knowledge base –KB- and industry processes activating data mining algorithms and big data systems able to provide gain of knowledge. The proposed work concerns the development of the highly performing Cassandra big data system collecting data of two industry location. Data are processed by data mining algorithms in order to formulate a decision making system oriented on call center human resources optimization and on customer service improvement. Correlation Matrix, Decision Tree and Random Forest Decision Tree algorithms have been applied for the testing of the prototype system by finding a good accuracy of the output solutions. The Rapid Miner tool has been adopted for the data processing. The work describes all the system architectures adopted for the design and for the testing phases, providing information about Cassandra performance and showing some results of data mining processes matching with industry BI strategies.

KEYWORDS

Big Data Systems, Cassandra Big Data, Data Mining, Correlation Matrix, Decision Tree, Frascati Guideline.

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Experimental study of Data clustering using k-Means and modified algorithms

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ABSTRACT

The k- Means clustering algorithm is an old algorithm that has been intensely researched owing to its ease and simplicity of implementation. Clustering algorithm has a broad attraction and usefulness in exploratory data analysis. This paper presents results of the experimental study of different approaches to k- Means clustering, thereby comparing results on different datasets using Original k-Means and other modified algorithms implemented using MATLAB R2009b. The results are calculated on some performance measures such as no. of iterations, no. of points misclassified, accuracy, Silhouette validity index and execution time.

KEYWORDS

Data Mining, Clustering Algorithm, k- Means, Silhouette Validity Index.

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MACHINE LEARNING TECHNIQUES FOR ANALYSIS OF EGYPTIAN FLIGHT DELAY

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ABSTRACT

Flight delay has been the fiendish problem to the world's aviation industry, so there is very important significance to research for computer system predicting flight delay propagation. Extraction of hidden information from large datasets of raw data could be one of the ways for building predictive model. This paper describes the application of classification techniques for analysing the Flight delay pattern in Egypt Airline's Flight dataset. In this work, four decision tree classifiers were evaluated and results show that the REPTree have the best accuracy 80.3% with respect to Forest, Stump and J48. However, four rules based classifiers were compared and results show that PART provides best accuracy among studied rule-based classifiers with accuracy of 83.1%. By analysing running time for all classifiers, the current work concluded that REPTree is the most efficient classifier with respect to accuracy and running time. Also, the current work is extended to apply of Apriori association technique to extract some important information about flight delay. Association rules are presented and association technique is evaluated.

KEYWORDS

Airlines, Flight delay, WEKA, Bigdata, Data mining, classification Algorithms , J48,Random Forest, Decision Stump, Ripper rule, Association rules, priori, Confusion matrix.

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